

coefficient (r) between the two variables $-U_o$ and T_m is 0.94 to indicate a very satisfactory linear relationship.

Results and Discussion

As is clear from Table 1, the values of $-U_o/T_m$ for different 3d metal(II) oxides appear to show a general close agreement with each other. The ratio observed in case of Fe(II)O, however, has a significant trend and needs an explanation. $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.56$, obtained therein, may either be due to higher lattice energy, $-U_o$, or lower melting point T_m . Since $-U_o$ used is derived from a reliable Born-Haber procedure⁴, the T_m value of Fe(II)O should be of doubtful accuracy. Literature does reveal that pure sample of iron oxide with an exact 1:1 stoichiometry is not known in actual practice^{7,8} to support the assumption made earlier.

Out of the oxides included in Table 1, Fe(II)O is reported to be devoid of true equilibrium and an attempt to produce it results in disproportionation to α -iron and ferrous oxide richer in oxygen content⁹. It is probably due to this fact that the properties of non-stoichiometric phase of ferrous oxide do change remarkably⁹ as compared to its expected 1:1 ideal stoichiometric phase. The vitiated ratio of $-U_o/T_m$, obtained for FeO, is thus quite clear. Ferrous oxide possesses a nearly constant composition of Fe_{0.95}O instead of FeO over a high temperature range of 900-1300 K, whereas for other companion oxides viz., Ni(II)O, Co(II)O and Zn(II)O, the departures from normal stoichiometry of 1:1 is relatively much insignificant^{10,11} even upto 1273 K. In Zn(II)O, for example, deviation from normal stoichiometry of the excess of zinc over oxygen is only $7 \times 10^{-3}\%$. It may thus be safely concluded that contrary to Fe(II)O, the other oxides of the family appear to show no net non-stoichiometry upto their melting points to observe a well behaved average constancy of $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$.

The maximum and minimum deviations of the average ratio are within 5%, except for FeO. A correspondence of lattice energy at the absolute melting points is thus satisfactorily established conforming to a general relation given by $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$. For the reason given earlier, one would disregard FeO as a regular member of the family for which the anomalous $-U_o/T_m$ value of 0.56, being about 22% higher than the average $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$, is perhaps a direct evidence to it. Using the relation, $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$, in conjunction with $-U_o^\ddagger$ of Fe(II)O tends to predict the ideal melting point of a conceptually synthesised sample of this oxide to be 2073 K which is meaningfully higher than the experimental T_m value⁶ of 1693 K. This is what one should demand from a well-known defective stoichiometry of FeO. Similarly, on assuming the principle of similarity, the hypothetical melting points of V(II)O and Cu(II)O should be around 2060 and 2180 K, respectively. The T_m data, thus predicted, are in fair agreement with those obtained from eqn. (2).

Further, it is interesting to compare the observed numerical values of $-U_o/T_m$ in s, d and f block metal-oxides. The overall mean values of $-U_o/T_m$ for the oxides of alkaline earths¹ (s² metals), 3d metal(II) oxides and 4f metal(III) oxides⁸ are 0.30, 0.46 and 1.23, respectively. The successive involvement of metals coupled with s, d and f orbital characteristics among the oxides of three categories tend to increase the $-U_o/T_m$ ratios in a very significant manner. A similar trend is followed by s and d block metals as well, whose respective $-U_o/T_m$ values^{1,2} are 0.41 and 0.66.

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Studies on Azo Derivatives of 1-Hydroxyanthracene

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WE report here the synthesis and spectral properties of eight new azo derivatives of 1-hydroxyanthracene.

Synthesis of 1-hydroxyanthracene: It was prepared by sulphonation of anthraquinone in presence

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TABLE 1—4-ARYLAZO-1-HYDROXYANTHRACENE

Sl. No.	X	m.p. °C	Absorption spectra				Characteristic frequencies in ir spectra cm^{-1}	Fluorescence spectra in ethanol	
			λ_{max} Ethanol nm	$\epsilon_{\text{max}} \times 10^4$	λ_{max} Acetone nm	$\epsilon_{\text{max}} \times 10^4$		Emission	Excitation
1.	2-nitro	240(d)	495	1.25	490	2.25	1590, 1620	383, 400, 430	338, 350, 370
2.	2-chloro	250(d)	495	6.00	480	6.00	1600, 1640	380, 410, 420	335, 350, 370
3.	3-chloro	223-3(d)	505	4.80	490	5.20	1595, 1620	387, 405, 425	335, 350, 375
4.	4-chloro	275(d)	515	4.00	505	4.08	3405, 1450	385, 405, 425	335, 350, 370
5.	2,3-dichloro	250(d)	485	2.76	470	3.44	1600, 1630	350, 370, 390	313
6.	2,4-dichloro	179(d)	510	1.80	505	2.00	1600, 1620	—	—
7.	2,6-dichloro	198-201(d)	495	3.68	485	4.8	1590, 1620	—	—
8.	4-methoxy	145(d)	530	2.96	525	3.26	1590, 1610	360, 380, 410	340, 360

There was good agreement between % C, H, N found and required.

d = decomposition.

Melting points are uncorrected.

of yellow mercuric oxide¹ followed by reduction to anthracene-1-sulphonic acid² and then fusion with potassium hydroxide to yield 1-hydroxyanthracene³.

Synthesis of 4-arylazo-1-hydroxyanthracene: The diazotisation was carried out in the usual way by dissolving aromatic amine in dilute HCl and adding sodium nitrite solution at 0 to 5°. The coupling was carried out in alcoholic medium. To an alcoholic solution of 1-hydroxyanthracene, aromatic diazonium chloride solution was slowly added at 0 to 5° with constant stirring. After complete addition, the mixture was stirred for 1 hr. The precipitate obtained was filtered and dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution (5%). The solution, after filtration, was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The precipitates obtained were filtered again and washed with distilled water till the filtrate was free from acid. The precipitates were dried at 40° under vacuum. These were crystallised till a constant melting point was obtained.

The absorption spectra of these derivatives were taken on a Spekol spectrophotometer using 10 mm cell in alcohol and in acetone. The absorption maxima values are recorded in Table 1. The ir spectra were scanned on a Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer in nujol mull. The fluorescence spectra (emission and excitation) were taken on a Aminco fluorescence spectrophotometer using alcohol as a solvent.

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Reactions of Arylpropargylthioether : Synthesis of Some 1,6-bis-derivatives of Hexa-2,4-diyne

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WHILE working on the reactions of derivatives of 1,4-dichloro-2-butyne¹ we have synthesized various sulphides, sulfoxides^{2,3}, sulphones^{4,5} and N-alkylanilino derivatives⁶⁻⁸. In continuation of this work we undertook the synthesis of various 1,6-bis-substituted hexa-2,4-diyne. We report here the synthesis of I, II, III, IV, V and VI.

The key compound 1,6-bis-(aryltio)-hexa-2,4-diyne (I) has been prepared by the Glaser oxidative coupling⁹ of arylpropargylthioether¹⁰ with Cu(II)-acetate-in pyridine-methanol (Scheme 1).

Oxidation of I with one equivalent of *m*-chloro-peroxybenzoic acid in methylene chloride at room temperature gave a mixture of unreacted disulphide (I, 20-25%), 1-aryltio-6-arylsulphoxido-2,4-hexadiyne (II, 35-40%) and 1,6-bis(arylsulphoxido)-hexa-2,4-diyne (IV, 15-20%). When I was oxidised with two equivalents of the peracid, 78-81% of 1,6-bis(arylsulphoxido)-hexa-2,4-diyne (IV), 8-12% of 1-arylsulphoxido-6-arylsulphonyl-hexa-2,4-diyne (V) and a small